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RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: QUAYSON****FIRST NAME: DAVID****PROGRAM CODE: DMCR****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: ONE****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA**

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Edit or delete text to show actual information below:

The author applied UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did not use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author did not use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 14%

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

List your 7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP) (samples below):

1. Starting A Good Academic Essay (EUCLID 2024, 7-12)
2. Some Rules of Thumb for Writing a Paper (EUCLID 2024, 12-14)
3. Proper Application of Punctuation in Essay Writing (EUCLID 2024, 15-23)
4. The Appropriate Usage of American and British English in Essay Writing (EUCLID 2024, 24-32)
5. Plagiarism In Academic Writing (EUCLID 2024, 33-39)
6. Adopting A Good Style Guide (EUCLID 2024, 40-42)

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WRITING ACADEMIC ESSAY

1) INTRODUCTION

I have looked at the content of the ACA-401/ACA-401D course pack, revised by Prof. Laurent Cleenewerck and Dr. Kabiru Gulma, and also watched the tutorial video, which Prof. Laurent Cleenewerck instructed. Reading and watching the course pack and video has introduced me to other dimensions of academic essay writing, which I believe will help me master my writing skills. I observed that to develop a good essay, one has to familiarise oneself with some of the basic requirements of essay writing. Also, I should be able to identify and adequately apply punctuation marks. However, knowing there are two major standard English versions, the American and the United Kingdom versions, I will decide and follow through with the essay on the type of English version I choose. The two will not mix up.

On the other hand, plagiarism is a no-go area when writing academically, as this will attract penalties in various forms. Furthermore, my writing style must be consistent, so I must adopt a style guide. In doing so, I have to follow guided rules, which will

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document my writing approach. Knowing some Latin words frequently used in English writing will help me apply them properly.

Throughout my academic journey, I have had to research and write a paper on selected topics. At each stage of my studies, I was introduced to some writing skills based on a particular writing style accepted by the institution. I have always wanted to pursue a Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) programme even though I know this quest will require much preparation that will involve a lot of reading and writing. After getting admission into EUCLID and getting introduced to all that is essential to embark on a successful PhD course, I have realised the enormous task set ahead and the need to be diligent in meeting this all-important requirement. I accessed the CMS and LMS with the attendant videos and read all the materials provided. Though I am required to do a lot of reading and writing, I am encouraged by the course materials and videos provided and how they are explained to make understanding easy.

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This paper will discuss concepts I have read from the course pack for period one and the introductory tutorial video. In this response paper, I will consider six significant ideas that I have studied from the ACA-401/ACA-401D course pack for period one (1) and the introductory tutorial video. These will include starting a good academic essay, following some rules of Thumb for writing a paper and applying proper punctuation in essay writing. Others include appropriate use of American and British English in essay writing, academic integrity, and adopting a good style guide.

2) STARTING A GOOD ACADEMIC ESSAY

There are many types of essays. However, “Academic essay or scholarly writing is nonfictional writing produced as part of academic work” (EUCLID 2024, 7). The EUCLID (2024, 7) states, “Nearly all academic writing shares some formal prose register, citations and references to other works, use of stable rhetorical moves to define the project’s scope, position it in relevant research, and advance new contributions.” Writing academic papers, I must admit, does not come by quickly. I agree that to achieve good results in time, starting an academic essay as early as possible after doing enough reading, further research, and thinking is important. It is never advisable to procrastinate. On the other hand, this must involve an initial plan, which should include “your initial thoughts and ideas about the research topic, which should constitute your preliminary essay plan that will help guide your research” (EUCLID 2024, 8).

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Furthermore, to produce an excellent academic essay, one needs to know which materials will benefit the chosen area, and so do extensive readings. Knowing the materials is important since writing on the selected area will be cumbersome and time-consuming without the relevant materials. You should avoid considering only the works that support your line of argument but look at other works that disagree with yours. Just look at it and see what you can learn from their arguments. You need access to sound evidence to support your argument and focus on the parts you deem fit to write on at this stage. Make notes while reading and highlight relevant information. Then draft the essay into three main parts: introduction, body, and conclusion. To ensure the whole essay flows, one needs to

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write in a logical order, proofread the drafted work by oneself, and ask another to assist in cross-checking spelling and key points required to produce a good essay.

I am informed and agree that studying how to start writing a good academic essay will go a long way to improving my writing skills and enhancing my work. However, to strengthen this skill further, I need to understand the rules of thumb.

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3) SOME RULES OF THUMB FOR WRITING A PAPER

The ACA-401/ACA-401D course pack for period one (1) discusses some rules of Thumb for writing a paper. The rules suggest that one must create a clear and succinct thesis statement to guide the writing, which must have a related theory.

Ask all the relevant questions related to writing to ascertain you have covered all that is required, keeping in mind the submission day for the assignment and to whom you are submitting. Further, one should acquaint oneself with all the necessary processes mandatory to the institution concerning how to present assignments. Nevertheless, it is important to be careful how I treat and argue about other writers' prepositions by not looking at them as not articulating themselves well but rather arguing to draw reasonable conclusions (EUCLID 2024, 14). Accordingly, using the correct grammar and punctuation, one must write in clear and concise language, ensuring that the writing is free of grammatical and punctuation errors.

Even though I have done some research work in the past, I have not taken time to look at the rules of thumb. Reading through the write-up has informed me how to organise my academic writing from now on. Moreover, consulting other writing styles with the proper inclusion of punctuation marks in academic writing will broaden my knowledge of good essay writing.

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4) PROPER APPLICATION OF PUNCTUATION IN ESSAY WRITING

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Punctuation marks in academic writings improve readability, convey the right tone, and elucidate the proper meaning of statements and phrases. To ensure fewer or no errors in the writing, one must consider the correct usage of grammar and punctuation marks. Therefore, knowing and getting familiar with all the punctuation marks and their usage is essential in academic writing.

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One must get to know how to use commas to separate items in a list and separate independent clauses. The proper application and use of semicolons to separate closely related independent clauses and to separate items in a list when using commas within the items will bring clarity to the sentence. The use of the colon in writing relates to that of the semicolon. One can use a colon to introduce a list or a quotation to emphasise a point or introduce an explanation in the essay. One must use a colon. To further add clarity to one's writings, it is proper to master the use and application of the apostrophe in sentences

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(EUCLID 2024, 17). The application of apostrophes should be to form possessive nouns and contractions. Nonetheless, properly introducing quotation marks to quote direct speech and text from a source will prevent Plagiarism and make one's work authentic. I have noted others, like the use of parenthesis, which helps to provide additional information that is not essential to the sentence and clarify meaning. Others also use dashes to indicate a range and break in thought when studied and applied, which will help in writing logically and coherently (EUCLID 2024, 17).

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Based on the above, it is evident that one cannot write a good essay without the correct use of punctuation marks. I am glad I know these so I can apply them correctly to my essays using the appropriate English language.

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5) THE APPROPRIATE USAGE OF AMERICAN AND BRITISH ENGLISH IN ESSAY WRITING

Coming from Ghana, a former British colony, I have always interacted and done my writing in British English. However, with the increasing influence of America in the world space, American English is the dominant English language in the world. The use of Standard American English within international academic parlance is due to the effect of America on the world today. The two versions are more similar than different (EUCLID 2024, 25). The key differences between the two versions of English lie in usage and general application of vocabulary, spelling, grammar, and punctuation. This difference sometimes confuses me in my writing, spelling, and application of clauses. Reading through the course pack for period one, I realised the choice and usage of Standard American English (SAE) and Standard British English (SBE) in research may depend on the reasons for writing, who is writing, and to whom one writes. Thus, selecting a particular English may depend on the native language or the language in which the researcher may be most comfortable writing. The only rule here is that choosing one language must be followed through to the end of the essay. The course pack has enlightened me on some of the differences in pronunciation, spelling, and meanings of some words in both languages. I have noted commas and periods in the two versions of English, too (EUCLID 2024, 28).

It is instructive to know from the course pack that I can effectively use one particular English language if I successfully master the rudiments of the language and apply it correctly in my essays. I will, therefore, consciously master and follow the rules governing these languages so I can use them appropriately while seriously considering academic integrity, thus avoiding plagiarism.

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6) PLAGIARISM IN ACADEMIC WRITING

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Every academic work must establish originality in thought and creativity and not the usage and quoting of sources that are not acknowledged. Therefore, everyone embarking on academic writing should rely on honesty and trust. If this is not adhered to, it will constitute plagiarism. According to EUCLID (2021, 34), Plagiarism is "when the writer uses a source of information without giving credit to the author of that source of

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information.” Plagiarism involves passing off someone else’s ideas, words, or work as your own, which may encompass usurping intellectual property rights. Plagiarism is a serious academic offence that can have severe consequences. Sanctions for Plagiarism depend on the level of offence. Plagiarism can undermine one’s credibility as a researcher, kill trust, and affect one’s academic and professional reputation. To avoid plagiarism, one needs to acknowledge the work of other scholars and validate their intellectual property. I concur that originality in my thoughts or writing can help prevent Plagiarism.

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Therefore, I must adequately acknowledge all citations in my writing to avoid Plagiarism and its attendant consequences. I have to recognise and appreciate the efforts of others by citing and using their works properly. In all these, I must seek to be original in my writing, applying the proper style guide as much as possible to enable me to build and add to existing knowledge.

7) ADOPTING A GOOD STYLE GUIDE

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The right writing style must guide the writer of an essay. Accordingly, The EUCLID recommended guide is the Chicago Rules (Turabian), although one may also use other internationally recognised Rules. EUCLID (2024, 41) intimates that a style guide documents your approach to some aspects of writing style that need consistency. The area one is writing on is to direct the type of style guides to use. It, however, encompasses the proper use of all required to have a good sentence, paragraph, and a paper or an essay.

It is my first time learning about Chicago Rules, and I look forward to learning and mastering all the rules so that I can apply them well in my writing.

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8) CONCLUSION

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The content of the ACA-401/ACA-401D course pack and the tutorial video has informed me what to expect going forward on the course. I plan to significantly improve my writing skills after finishing the first course. I have made it my number one reference material throughout this doctoral programme.

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The course pack taught me how to start writing a good academic essay using the rules of Thumb. This session taught me the need to consult other writing styles with the proper use of punctuation marks in academic writing. It has further helped me to know how to effectively use one particular English language in my writing by consciously mastering and following the language rules while avoiding Plagiarism through academic integrity. To do this well, I must master the Chicago Rules (Turabian).

The ACA-401/ACA-401D course pack period (1) and the tutorial video have been very instructive and eye-opening regarding academic writing. The course pack was well written and gave the correct information required for this course, even though I have so much to learn and unlearn. To fully apprise myself of the content of the course material, I will read over and watch the video many times.

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